

Implementation of a text analysis process using R for search strategy development in systematic reviews: Protocol

Claudia Kapp, Naomi Fujita-Rohwerder, Wiebke Sieben, Siw Waffenschmidt, Elke Hausner

Corresponding author

Claudia Kapp

E-mail: claudia.kapp@iqwig.de

Im Mediapark 8, 50670 Cologne, Germany

Citation

Claudia Kapp, Naomi Fujita-Rohwerder, Wiebke Sieben, Siw Waffenschmidt, Elke Hausner. Implementation of a text analysis process using R for search strategy development in systematic reviews: Protocol. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7762286>

Abstract

A systematic review is based on comprehensive information retrieval. One of the main tasks in information retrieval is the development of search strategies for systematic literature searches in bibliographic databases. This includes the identification of free-text terms and keywords. The methods for developing search strategies applied by the German health technology assessment agency, the Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Health Care (IQWiG) [1,2] are based on established methods for developing and validating study filters [3]. The text analysis software Wordstat is used for search strategy development, but the actual development of a strategy is still iterative, i.e. subjective, due to a lack of technical options.

To further refine the objective approach, the aim of our project is to develop a text analysis tool for search strategy development using the programming language “R”. To this end, we will take the following steps: The first will be to define the core functions required for search strategy development. In a second step, we will identify existing R packages that are suitable to form the basis of the functions required for our package. We will then identify gaps that cannot be filled by existing packages and create the code to provide the required functions. The next step is to compile all functions to Version 1.0 of the package, including evaluation of the R package and subsequent creation of a graphical user interface (“Shiny App”). Subsequently, further development is planned of additional functions for the R package in a version 2.0 as a proof of concept.

1 Background

Systematic reviews (SRs) aim to inform evidence-based decision-making in health care. Information retrieval for SRs needs to be conducted in a systematic way to identify all relevant studies on the question of interest; one of the main tasks is to develop strategies for systematic searches in bibliographic databases.

The German health technology assessment agency, the Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Health Care (IQWiG) bases its methods for developing search strategies [1,2] on established techniques for developing and validating study filters [3]. These search strategies include free-text terms and keywords. Search terms are identified for search concepts. The relevant search terms are automatically generated using a gold standard (relevant articles already known). This is done using proprietary text analysis software (Wordstat 8 [4]), which provides simple word frequencies and word combinations. In addition, the potentially relevant search terms can be compared to a control set from PubMed.

The strengths of the objective approach are that it is transparent, allows informed decisions to be made about the inclusion (or omission) of terms, and allows information specialists to work more independently [2]. However, the actual development of a search strategy using Wordstat is still iterative, due to a lack of technical options.

The aim of the current project is to implement a new text analysis process for the development of search strategies in systematic reviews. Prior to the start of the project, an internal workshop was organised where IQWiG information specialists defined their requirements for new information retrieval tools to help them cope with their workload. They noted that new tools should make their work easier, while at the same time maintaining high quality. To achieve this, the tools should be flexible and compatible with existing tools and workflows. Customised solutions can be challenging due to the financial and human resources required. Natural language processing (NLP) approaches tailored to information retrieval needs may be a promising option.

In addition, information specialists are increasingly exploiting the potential of open source applications, where the source code is freely available. This allows both customisation and verification of methodological procedures. IQWiG has identified R [5] as the most suitable option for its requirements. R has become an established programming language in statistical computing, including text analysis for search strategy development. Using R to update the text analysis process has many advantages. For example, it is more flexible than other data analysis tools (e.g. SAS, SPSS, STATA) and allows easy implementation of customised solutions. R-based methods are being further developed and presented in scientific publications (e.g. [6]), and meetings (e.g. ESMAR Conference).

2 Objectives

To further refine the objective approach, the aim of our project is to develop a text analysis tool for search strategy development using R.

3 Procedure

3.1 Identifying available R packages for implementing text analysis

To date, the R package "quanteda" has been found to be particularly useful for text analysis [7,8]. We will search for other relevant R packages based on an exploratory search of the CRAN server [9] and the project group's previous experiences of evidence synthesis using R.

3.2 Identifying functional and non-functional requirements for text analysis

We will update the functional text analysis requirements for search strategy development based on the experience of IQWiG's information specialists.

The following requirements have already been implemented in the current process using Wordstat 8:

- Word frequency calculation
- 2-word frequency (single term, multiple term, phrases)
- Frequency information per reference, title, abstract, keywords (single, joint)
- Partial analysis: title, abstract, keywords and combination of title/abstract
- Export function for statistical calculations
- Statistical comparison of the test set with a norm set

The following requirements have yet to be implemented:

- Truncated word frequency (word stem only)
- 2-3 word combination with Boolean operators AND
- 2-3 word combination with adjacent (ADJ)
- Consideration of the "explode" function
- Calculation of sensitivity, specificity and accuracy
- Discriminatory analysis of relevant and non-relevant hits
- Presentation of which new relevant hits are found with which (combination of) search terms.

3.3 Adapting the identified R package functions

The functional requirements will be compared with the current functions of available R packages, providing an opportunity to check the text analysis process and identify any potential need for updates at each stage of the process. Suitable R packages will then be selected to further develop functions. An updated workflow in R for search strategy development will then be created with the aim of routine use. This workflow will be implemented as a new R package to allow easy compilation and installation for users. The initial aim is to produce a Version 1.0 of an R package replacing Wordstat for search strategy development at IQWiG. In a next step, the R functions will be further developed in Version 2.0 (see Section 4).

3.4 Creating a user interface ("Shiny App") for routine use of R functions

The R package should have a graphical user interface ("Shiny App") [10] so that the functions can be used without knowledge of R. There are several ways to do this. For example, an app can be started locally within a development framework (e.g. RStudio [11]). Users need a current version of R, the development framework, and the necessary R packages on their computer. Alternatively, a web app can be used that can be accessed via an organization's internal network, which requires setting up a Shiny Server (possibly using a Docker container). The advantage of a web app is that it is easier to use and requires less maintenance. A second way to deploy a web app is via an external server host (e.g. shinyapps.io by Posit [12]); however, external server services are usually not free of charge.

3.5 Developing a concept and workflow for regular updates of text analysis processes

The R programming language is constantly evolving and it is therefore necessary to develop a concept for updating the R package created so that the newer versions of R can continue to be used.

3.6 Evaluating the R package

We will evaluate the R package by means of at least 10 IQWiG projects for which text analysis is already available. The focus will be on the comparability of the results of the text analysis using R and Wordstat based on the characteristic values from the frequency table and the statistical comparison using the norm set ("z values"). The evaluation should show whether the quality of the results of the new process is comparable to the "gold standard". In addition, we will examine whether the performance of the R package (speed, error rate, stability, etc.) and the ease of use are satisfactory.

4 Outlook

The next step will be to think ahead and further develop additional functions in an R package Version 2.0 as a proof of concept. This will focus on issues such as automation of test set

creation and automated identification of phrases and search term combinations with regard to the quality criteria of information retrieval (e.g. precision, recall, F-value). To this end, we may present the project status at a hackathon, i.e. an event where internal and external software developers work together to create software solutions. This is a low-threshold way to involve external experts.

Bibliography

1. Simon M, Hausner E, Klaus SF et al. Identifying nurse staffing research in Medline: development and testing of empirically derived search strategies with the PubMed interface. *BMC Med Res Methodol* 2010; 10: 76. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1186/1471-2288-10-76>.
2. Hausner E, Waffenschmidt S, Kaiser T et al. Routine development of objectively derived search strategies. *Syst Rev* 2012; 1: 19. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1186/2046-4053-1-19>.
3. Jenkins M. Evaluation of methodological search filters: a review. *Health Info Libr J* 2004; 21(3): 148-163. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1471-1842.2004.00511.x>.
4. Provalis Research. WordStat: Version 8.0.35 [Software]. 2022.
5. The R Foundation. The R Project for Statistical Computing [online]. [Accessed: 24 Feb 2023]. URL: <https://www.r-project.org/>.
6. Grames EM, Stillman AN, Tingley MW et al. An automated approach to identifying search terms for systematic reviews using keyword co-occurrence networks. *Methods Ecol Evol* 2019; 10(10): 1645-1654. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/2041-210x.13268>.
7. Watanabe K, Müller S. Quanteda Tutorials [online]. 2023 [Accessed: 24 Feb 2023]. URL: <https://tutorials.quanteda.io/>.
8. Benoit K, Watanabe K, Wang H et al. quanteda: An R package for the quantitative analysis of textual data. *Journal of Open Source Software* 2018; 3(30): 774. <https://dx.doi.org/10.21105/joss.00774>.
9. The Comprehensive R Archive Network [online]. [Accessed: 24 Feb 2023]. URL: <https://cran.r-project.org/index.html>.
10. Chang W, Cheng J, Allaire J et al. shiny: Web Application Framework for R; R package version 1.7.4 [online]. 2022 [Accessed: 24 Feb 2023]. URL: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=shiny>.
11. Posit Software. RStudio IDE; The most trusted IDE for open source data science [online]. 2022 [Accessed: 06 Feb 2023]. URL: <https://posit.co/products/open-source/rstudio/>.
12. Posit Software. shinyapps.io [online]. 2022 [Accessed: 06 Feb 2023]. URL: <https://www.shinyapps.io/>.